

THE MAIN REASON FOR THE DEMAND FOR ORGANIC PRODUCTS?

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Abstract: Organic agricultural products are currently the fastest growing market segment, and despite the low productivity of organic products compared to conventional products and the difference in prices, the demand of consumers for this type of products is increasing in recent years. It is associated with the negative impact on the health of many people due to the consumption of agricultural products. In order to meet the demand of consumers for organic products, reforms are being carried out in our country based on world experiences.

Keywords: Organic agriculture, traditional agriculture, food safety, pesticides and...

The intensification of agriculture has significantly increased the supply of food to the world's population in recent decades. Uzbekistan is also increasing the volume of exports of agricultural products, while fully supplying its population with food products. Along with all sectors, the food industry is also developing rapidly, but as a result of intensive development of agriculture, excessive production of reactive nitrogen, pollution of land and water, greenhouse gas emissions and biological diversity. Consequently of the loss of diversity and excessive use of chemicals over the years, it has been confirmed that it has had a negative impact on the flora and fauna, human health, and ecology.

Organic agriculture is offered as an alternative to conventional agriculture. This is one of the most reliable ways to transition to a green economy, which will significantly reduce environmental risks and increase the well-being of human society. We must emphasize that the implementation of organic farming requires many changes throughout the food chain, from producers to final consumers. That is, the effect can be achieved only through the active participation of not only organic product growers, but also all process participants.

The use of artificial mineral fertilizers, pesticides, genetically modified organisms, food additives, growth regulators, chemical agents, radioactive rays, sewage sludge is prohibited in the production of organic agricultural products, and as a result of the production of organic products preservation of biological diversity, significant increase of soil fertility, readiness for various vagaries of nature by searching for resistant varieties and offspring, and using biological methods to protect plants, and a positive effect on the health of plants, animals and people it is impossible to achieve. Organic products contain more vitamins and various microelements compared to conventionally grown agricultural products, and their advantages in terms of taste and quality are of particular importance.

As a result of the large amount of chemical substances used in the production of traditional agricultural products, many diseases occur in humans and require revolutionary changes in terms of food safety. Among such diseases, scientists prove in their research that they are related to pesticides in food production, such as Parkinson's disease, some type of

diabetes and cancer, childhood leukemia and lymphoma, behavioral disorders, autism, and children's allergies. It has been proven that the use of pesticides has a long-term negative effect on the brain activity, height growth, and sexual development of the children of greenhouse workers. At the same time, insecticides are designed to be toxic to the brain development of insects, and many herbicides and fungicides have also been shown to have a negative effect on the nervous system. Pesticides of various kinds have neurological effects on adults, and it is not difficult to imagine that all of these can have a significant effect on the activity of the developing brain. According to scientists, about 200,000 people die every year from acute pesticide poisoning. As a solution to the above problems, one of the most urgent issues of today is the transfer of farms engaged in practical agriculture to organic agriculture. Developed countries such as the European Union and the United States have achieved remarkable results in this direction. A number of measures have been taken to ensure food safety in the European Union. The organic agriculture development policy has led to a reduction in pesticide residues in food. In our country, various reforms are being carried out for the development of this industry. With the help of the methods used in the cultivation of organic products, pollution of water and land resources and release of harmful substances into the environment are prevented. This is of great importance in increasing food safety, and reflects the benefits of both producers and consumers.

In conclusion, we can say that:

- workers working on organic farms do not use chemicals, so their occupational health is improved, as a result of which they are able to perform their activities with quality and on time.

- the vitamins and other trace elements contained in organic products improve the health of consumers, especially the abundance of amino acids in organic products helps prevent cancer and other diseases, and residents of Uzbekistan will have the opportunity to buy high-quality, pesticide-free products.

- with the help of organic agricultural methods, pollution of land, water, animals and atmospheric air is prevented, as a result of which it is possible to achieve a gradual increase in productivity and the cultivation of crops resistant to various natural disasters.

- the possibility of increasing the country's export potential through the cultivation of organic products will increase, and the ground will be created for foreign currency to enter our country and the income sources of farmers will increase....

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Organic Products
2. V.Vigar. S. Myers et al. A systematic review of organic versus conventional food consumption: whether there are measurable benefits to human health.
3. H.Torjuse, A.L.Brantsæter, M.Haugen, J. Alexander and others Reduced risk of pre-eclampsia with organic vegetable consumption: results from the prospective Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study
4. E.A. Kolesnikova The influence of organic products on the quality of human life.
5. A. Rahman. P. Baharloui et al. Comprehensive analysis of organic food products, assessment of nutritional value and impact on human health.
6. S. T. Iskandarov, G. Sadikova

7. "The World of Organic Agriculture" Source: The Dairy News 8. A.Yu. Egorov. Formation and development of the market for organic agri-food products:
8. T.M. Svechnikova Analysis of the global market for the production of organic products 2019
9. M.R. Amanovich, R.D. Nazaralievich PRODUCTION OF ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN VEGETABLE GROWING
- 10.C. Badgley, J. Moghtader, E. Quintero, E. Zakem, M. J. Chappell, K. Avilés-Vázquez, A. Samulon, I. Perfecto, Organic agriculture and the global food supply. *Renew. Agr. Food Syst.* 22, 86–108 (2007).
11. N. E.-H. Scialabba, C. Hattam, Organic Agriculture, Environment and Food Security (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, 2002).
12. A. Trewavas, Urban myths of organic farming. *Nature* 410, 409–410 (2001).